

Whole-genome sequencing of *Bacillus velezensis* strain SD1 isolated from a non-rhizospheric soil in Algeria with biocontrol potential

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Abstract

This study reports the complete genome sequencing of *Bacillus velezensis* strain SD1 isolated from non-rhizospheric soil and sampled from the southeastern region of Algeria. The strain was selected for its powerful antagonistic activities against a wide range of phytopathogens. Whole genome sequencing offers new potential toward a deep understanding of the strain and provides valuable insights into its biocontrol mechanisms by revealing key genes that are pivotal to its effectiveness. The genome of *B. velezensis* strain SD1 was assembled to a total size of 3.97 Mb, distributed across 51 contigs with an N50 of 1,034,155 bp and a GC content of 46.38 %. These data were deposited on GenBank under the Project ID [PRJNA1332706](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/GenBank/PRJNA1332706) and will provide a useful resource to the field of soil microbiology.

Introduction

The *Bacillus* species are well known for their adaptability in diverse environments by producing resistant endospores. Through this ability, species of this genus are accorded long-term viability and adaptation to unfavourable environmental conditions (Iqbal *et al.*, 2023). This specific characteristic facilitates the biological preparation and storage of *Bacillus*-based commercial products, making them more useful for field applications compared to other microbial biocontrol agents (BCAs) (Pérez-García *et al.*, 2011). It is worth noting that half of the commercially available bacteria-based biological control agents are *Bacillus* species (Dame *et al.*, 2021).

Bacillus velezensis is a renowned species that has received considerable attention as a BCA. This species is distinguished by its unique genetic composition, demonstrated by the fact that a large portion of its genome (>8%) is devoted to the synthesis of specialized metabolites (Yang *et al.*, 2024). This metabolome is diverse and includes non-ribosomally synthesized polyketides and lipopeptides (fengycin, iturin, surfactin, macrolactin, and kurstakin), ribosomally synthesized bacteriocins, and volatile compounds. In addition, *B. velezensis* strains have also been noted for their production of fungi cell-wall degrading enzymes, making them promising candidates for agricultural usage as biocontrol agents (Keswani *et al.*, 2020; Miljaković *et al.*, 2020).

Whole genome sequencing has emerged as a powerful tool and reliable method for functional studies to identify biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs). BGCs are groups of genes responsible for encoding secondary metabolites and other bioactive molecules. This approach provides insights into the molecular mechanisms behind the biocontrol properties of antagonistic strains (Li *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, genome mining can also lead to antibiotic discovery and other potential genes involved in biocontrol. In this report, we present the whole genome sequencing

of *B. velezensis* strain SD1, isolated from non-rhizospheric soil of Djanet, Algeria. The strain was identified in a screen for candidates with activity against diverse plant pathogens (Ghozlani *et al.*, 2025). Genome mining will provide a deeper characterization of the strain and facilitate further investigation into its biocontrol activities.

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

Strain SD1 was isolated from non-rhizospheric soil sampled from Djanet (Algeria) (Ghozlani *et al.*, 2025).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Bacteria preparation and DNA processing were conducted following MicrobesNG protocols (Birmingham, UK; <https://microbesng.com>). Subsequent to library preparation, DNA sequencing, and bioinformatics were carried out by MicrobesNG. Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions with the following modifications: input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time increased to 45 seconds. Libraries were sequenced using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol. Reads were adapter-trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. De novo assembly was performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich *et al.*, 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Taxonomic nomenclature

The classification and the identification of the strain were carried out using the Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) calculator (Yoon *et al.*, 2017). This tool was employed to determine the OrthoANIu percentage between the Strain SD1 and the reference genome *B. velezensis* FZB42 (ASM1578v2; GCF_000015785.2). Additionally, the taxonomic nomenclature was confirmed through the PubMLST.org website (Jolley *et al.*, 2018).

Results

Genomic Features

A summary of the genomic features of the *B. velezensis* strain SD1 is provided in Table 1. The genome is assembled to 3,966,098 bp in length across 51 contigs. The number of protein-coding genes identified was 3,798; meanwhile, the GC content was 46.38%.

Data availability

The complete genome sequence of the SD1 strain of *B. velezensis* has been deposited in the NCBI GenBank under the accession numbers listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Genomic features of the *Bacillus velezensis* strain SD1 isolated from non-rhizospheric soil of Djanet (Algeria)

Bacterial species	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
Strain	SD1
Genome size (bp)	3,966,098
% GC	46.38
Number of contigs (≥ 1000 bp)	13
Largest contig (bp)	1,244,049
Mean coverage (X)	83.2928
Number of reads	722,345
N50 (bp)	1,034,155
CDS	3,798
tRNA number	86
tmRNA number	1
SRA accession number	SRR35552199

Assembly accession number	JBRILO000000000
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Taxonomic classification

Genomic sequencing allowed us to revise the taxonomy of this strain from *B. amyloliquefaciens* SD1 to *B. velezensis* SD1. The taxon identification of the SD1 strain is based on the OrthoANIu values (98.31%) and the MLST taxonomic nomenclature (Table 2a). Additionally, the Ribosomal MLST matching profile showed the membership of this strain to the species *velezensis* (Table 2b).

Table 2: Taxonomic identification of Strain *Bacillus velezensis* SD1.

a) Rank	Taxon	Support	Taxonomy
SPECIES	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus velezensis</i>

b) rST	193967
Genus	<i>Bacillus</i>
Species	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are available prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We welcome feedback from the community. For further information, please contact FN (fnateche@usthb.dz)

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